

IMPROVED DESIGN OF GATE VALVES THAT WORKS AT HIGH PRESSURE

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ABSTRACT

As a result of the uneven distribution of relative pressure on the working surface of the plug valve assembly operating under high pressure, the scale of wear increases and the performance of the structure decreases. The article required a solution to the problem and proposed a new improvement method. In the new design, the working stroke of the valve has been changed by ensuring joint deformation of the gate and ring. As a result, uniform pressure distribution was ensured between the gate and the seat.

Keywords: valve, service, fluid, steel, gate, wellhead, deformation, improve.

High-pressure valves used in the oil and gas industry are one of the critical components of the closing devices of Christmas tree equipment. Gate valves are the most common type of high-pressure closure device in industry. Valves of this type are installed above the Xmas tree and manifold operating under high pressure in an aggressive environment and are mainly divided into types ZMS, ZM, ZMAD.

The reliability of this unit ensures the reliability of the Christmas tree fixtures. Direct-flow valves operating under high pressure in aggressive environments are manufactured by various local foreign brand companies.

- Cameron Company. USA
- Company "BREDA". Italy

- Company "MALBRANK". France
- Company "QREY". France
- Company "FMS". England Wales
- Company "MC EVOY". USA
- Company "WKM". USA

One of the most experienced companies in the production of valves is "MALBRANK". To obtain an effective seal on the locking unit of the single-plate gate valve prepared by this company, the provided seal is provided according to the metal-to-metal principle. The spindle is seated on two support bearings. A loading valve has been added to the design of the valve above the roof, with the help of this valve the supply of lubricating oils to the casing becomes even easier.

Fig 1. "MALBRANK". France

Double plate gate valve manufactured by QREY. In this valve, the gate is made with side surface seals. In the design of this valve, the running nut is inserted into the bore between the valve gate plates. Provision is made for supplying lubricant to the valve casing and to the spindle sealing unit. The spindle is positioned motionless towards the output.

Fig 2. "QREY". France

The valve prepared by FMS belongs to the group in which sealing is ensured according to the metal-to-metal principle. This valve uses single-acting chevron collars to provide sealing.

Fig 3. "FMS". England Wales

The sealing assembly of the valve design, prepared by MC EVOY, creates a seal between the T-shape running nut seated on the wedge seat and the gate. These gates are placed in the bores of the valve casing. Provision is made for supplying lubricating oils. This valve has a valve at the bottom, like some other valves.

The valve spindles produced by this company are made with a fixed outlet and two plate gates. The running nut is located only above one of the two plates. The surfaces of these plates are made in the shape of a U, brought to the contact position and connected by an arcuate spring.

Fig 4. "MC EVOY". USA

Fig 5. "WKM". USA

Fig 6. "BREDA". Italy

The BREDA company recommends a gate valve that is movable towards the exit, that is, a gate valve with a spindle extending beyond the frame of the gate valve.

An analysis of the above-mentioned valves shows that the main reason for the loss of performance of these valves is the wear of its sealing unit - a pair of gate valves and a seat. The main reason for the wear of this pair:

1. Uneven distribution of force on the working surfaces of the mechanisms.
2. Aggressive environmental conditions.
3. Type of material of parts and assemblies.

Fig 7. Cameron Company. USA

The purpose of the research work is to solve the problem.

By changing the design of a direct-flow valve, ensure uniform distribution of relative pressure on its working surfaces.

From the point of view of the research carried out on the valve we selected from the Cameron company, it was revealed that in order to achieve novelty in the sealing unit of the valve design, a fundamental design change is required

Figure 7 shows a general view of a manually controlled single-plate gate valve manufactured by Cameron.

So, the design of the sealing unit needs to be changed in such a way that its operating principle changes. In our proposed valve design, a new ring was added between the gate-seat pairs; the design of this ring was chosen so that the ring bends between two surfaces together with the gate and ensures uniform distribution of relative pressure on the working surface of the gate.0020

Conclusions

1. As a result of the conducted research on the design of direct-flow valves, it was revealed that in order to improve their performance, improvement of their design is necessary.
2. The article presents a new design of a direct-flow valve with an elastic deformation capacity of the sealing unit.
3. A feature of this design is the change in its operating principle by joint deformation of the gate and ring.
4. This gate valves greater than other and they are normally provided with reduced (sometimes called conventional or standard) port in accordance with the minimum diameters specified in the reference standard (e.g., ISO 15761). Full port valves might be available at increased cost and delivery. These valves are also available with extended body outlets that can be used instead of gate valve plus pipe nipple assemblies.

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